

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11120825>

THE IMPACT OF CHINA'S SOFT POWER IN MODERN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

Akhmadalieva Sevinchbonu Rustamjon kizi

Master student of the UWED,
the chair of international relations and world politics.

Key words: *soft power, hard power, “harmonious society”, “going out” and “go global” strategies.*

Applying soft power in foreign policy has become a prevalent means in the relationship and cooperation among countries to exercise their powers without depending overwhelmingly on hard power. The concept of "soft power" was originally introduced by Joseph Nye in his book titled “Bound to Lead” in 1990. According to Nye, “soft power- getting others to want the outcomes that you want, coopts people rather than coerces them”. He distinguished between two forms of powers: soft power means that state A can use its intangible sources to charm state B without threatening or coercing. In contrast, hard power means that state A should force state B to do the favour of state A by threatening or coercing. This makes it clear that soft power is different from hard power in their sources and exercises. In other words, soft power is a valuable tool to make others do what you want without resorting to coercive measures.

In recent decade China's Interest in Soft Power has initiated massive efforts to enhance its soft power across the world in order to fulfil its national interests. These attempts started when former President of China Hu Jintao in 2004 and 2005 publically announced his intentions and aims to build a “harmonious society” and “a harmonious world”. According to Hu, a harmonious world would be characterized by multi-relationships, mutually advantageous cooperation, the spirit of inclusiveness to build a world in which coexistence among civilizations exists and by a reformed United Nations. In 2014, Xi announced that developing China's soft powers can be achieved through the state's ability in global communication and its capacity of building a good communication system. He also believes that new media can play this role by increasing creativity and presenting reliability of China's publicity and the China's stories, voices and characteristics should be well explained. Under Xi, China has introduced many new initiatives to the world, such as “the Asia-Pacific dream”, “the Chinese dream”, “the Twenty-First-Century Maritime Silk Road”, “the Silk Road

Economic Belt” and many others. It is easy to describe such terms as “slogan diplomacy,” but Beijing nevertheless attaches great meaning to it. Chinese leaders have soon realized that being a great power or even a powerful state in the region requires having hard power and soft power as well. By attracting neighbouring countries, China would reduce the United States’ influence in the region. As the largest country in Asia, China’s rapid economic growth is a good indicator of increasing its hard power and soft power in the region. Therefore, it cannot be overlooked that economic power beyond soft power plays a significant role in China’s diplomatic approach and its foreign relations. In order to promote its soft power China heavily needs economic power to support media broadcasting, cultural and art institutions both inside and outside the country. Chinese influence has increased in Asia over the last few decades through developing economic trades, providing aids to Asian countries and creating regional organizations. There are different ways to promote China’s culture among other nations around the world. This could be through media such as TV, Radios, Internet and film or through the establishment of cultural and language institutions in other countries. In 2004, China initiated a program to open Confucius Institutes in other countries, now it has more than 400 Confucius Institutes and 500 Confucius Classrooms in 120 countries. China plans to increase this number in the future in order to promote Chinese language and culture abroad. Some other efforts can be noticed is that it has established „24- hours Chinese TV and Radio broadcasting stations” to enhance its culture and language in other countries and also to attract international students. Education is another essential method to China’s soft power. In 2015, around 300,000 International students were studying in Chinese universities (the vast majority learning the Chinese language), with additional numbers in vocational colleges. Every year, the China Scholarship Council provides nearly 20,000 scholarships to international students. China has also become an active participation in „regional multilateral organization such as the Association of South- East Asian Nations (ASEAN). From this it can be seen that China has real intentions to promote its soft power and influence over other countries across the world through the diffusion and develop of its charm image. Moreover, China has taken some steps to increase its assistance and aid to other countries around the world particularly, in Southeast Asia, Latin America and Africa. Since 2010, China’s aid and assistance have increased dramatically. In 2009 China’s foreign aid was \$124.8 billion, it then increased to \$168.6 billion in 2010, it continued to grow to \$189.3 billion in 2011, while it was only \$1.7 billion in 2001. 2010 and 2011 figures were equivalent to about 3 percent of China’s GDP and were more than twice the size of the officially reported budget of defense ministry of the China. Moreover, China has pledged to spend large amounts of money on projects which are backing up its soft power. This includes \$150 billion for

projects like (the New Development Bank, the Silk Road Economic Belt, the Maritime Silk Road and the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank). China's influence over economy is the strongest instrument supporting its soft power ambitions as it can attract other countries through signing huge trades and investment deals as well as offering loans. What China Hopes to Achieve Chinese leaders have understood the limits of hard power to change other's behaviour, and the costly consequences of using it. Beijing is acutely aware of the necessity for a soft power approach to promote national interests in the 21st century. Soft power would benefit China's interests in several ways.

China's soft power is greatly manifested in its diplomatic strategy. The 'rejuvenation of the nation' is achieved through Beijing consensus, partnership initiatives, and spread of cultural values through Confucius institutes. It has focused upon the mechanisms of attraction. Diplomatically, it has started a 'charm offensive' towards partners and building their confidence in Chinese policy discourses, strategies and initiatives. China's emphasis on peaceful development, peaceful co-existence, and harmony provides a foundational basis universal in its appeal and can create a new set of principles that can facilitate the acceptance of morality in international politics. According to Chinese academics, Chinese external soft power consumption includes projecting and communicating its foreign policy positions on world issues, to build a good international image for China and moderating the external environment. As a part of Chinese 'going out' and 'go global' strategy, China has encouraged the mainstream media to enhance the coverage and generate potential favourable influence on the world opinion. Through this, China endeavors to potentially form a source of public influencing mechanisms. China has created many for a to promote its culture, language and traditions to the world through cultural exchange programs, sports, arts and performing art, music, film and literature. It also provides a platform for countless governmental and non-governmental seminars, conferences and dialogue centres for the interaction, cooperation and discussion of the Chinese people with the outside world. In this regard, Beijing Forum, Boao Forum for Asia, and China Development Forum can be mentioned as the few interactive dialogue sites with the purpose of developing a positive image for China. Besides these initiatives, China's heavy investment on educational exchanges, scholarships and research collaborations have earned a repute. Chinese government offers more than 20,000 scholarships to foreign students annually on a variety of subjects from science and technology to arts and social sciences. More specifically, scholarships for learning of Chinese language, literature and culture are more enthusiastically provided in China as well as in different foreign countries through the Confucian Institutes.

All in all, soft power is the power of persuasion and attraction. As it is dependent upon soft-image and international standing, China's soft national image building strategy is aimed at enhancing its soft power through public policy, promotion of culture and economic diplomacy. China is utilizing its soft power to attain the final goal of 'the rejuvenation of the nation'. Various states consider that China is a powerful country with capacity and ability to withstand the global challenges and can defy the threats and pressures posed by the powerful states such as the US. It can ensure the prosperity of its citizens and greater good for the world populace. It has also become a healthy contribution in the list of great powers that can resist the unilateral trends in the international system and ensure the stability of the international order. Its rise has provided other nations the opportunity to benefit from the socio-economic, developmental and infrastructure initiatives of China. Domestically, Chinese economic development patterns are on ascending. Through various regional initiatives along with regional partnerships and collaboration it has overcome its economic inequality between the coastal and rural areas. Its economic and diplomatic success has promoted a sense of pride and confidence among the population and has satisfied the ever-rising nationalism. Its promotion of cultural values and language has gained her a soft-image and a status of a benign power in many regions of the world.

REFERENCES

1. Blanchard, J.M., & Lu, F. Thinking hard about soft power: a review and critique of the literature on China and soft power. *Asian Perspective*.
2. Cheng, S.S. The approaches of China's soft power strategy. *An Interdisciplinary Journal*.
3. Cho, Y.N., & Jeong, J.H. China's soft power: discussions, resources, and prospects. *Asian Survey*.
4. Gil, J. The promotion of Chinese language learning and China's soft power. *Asian Social Science*.
5. Yongnian, Zheng, *China and International Relations: The Chinese view and the contribution of Wang Gungwu*, New York: Routledge Publications.